

RESEARCHING OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE PRACTICE OF IMPROVING SPEECH SKILLS OF STUDENTS OF NON- PHILOLOGICAL DIRECTION

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Abstract. *This article is due to researching foreign language practice of improving speech skills of students of non-philological direction. In modern information and communication conditions, the leading role is given to interactivity among students studying English, for the formation of a new type of teacher - a sociocultural personality.*

Keywords: *competency-based approach, cultural competence, cultural component, foreign language, non-philological students, professional development, quality of training, speech skills.*

Introduction: Fundamental reforms in the social and spiritual spheres of our country are aimed, first of all, at ensuring stability, well-being of the people and spiritual and moral growth of all citizens of society. For this purpose, higher education is tasked with training specialists who think in a modern way, who meet the needs of modern society, personnel of a new formation, active participants in all innovative changes taking place in the Republic.

The reforms carried out in the Republic, changes in the foreign policy of the state contributed to the expansion of international contacts, as a result of which the need for personnel with linguistic competence has increased. The need to improve linguistic transformation in all areas of development of language literacy of young personnel is noted in the regulatory documents of our country, defining the leading directions in improving language literacy, which required "improvement of educational standards, curricula and plans, textbooks, as well as modernization of pedagogical education, creation of advanced foreign educational centers for training in certain foreign languages". Also, the normative documents note that "...our society is open to interaction of different cultures, their dialogue and mutual enrichment". Therefore, teaching the basics of cultural dialogue is acquiring the status of a vital imperative in all areas of speech development in our time. Among the many aspects of teaching foreign language speech skills, it is necessary to highlight the etiquette of speech behavior. The etiquette of speech activity requires reference to the linguacultural aspect of its research and teaching. The etiquette of speech activity acts as one of the main means for mastering communicative and behavioral culture, has a deep character and is reflected in all components of foreign language speech activity: linguistic, sociolinguistic, sociocultural, discursive, strategic.

Therefore, by the linguacultural aspect of foreign language speech activity we mean the subcomponents of the noted components associated with foreign language speech activity, necessary for students to master English language (hereinafter referred to as FL) as a result of combining the skills of the native language and cultures with knowledge of the speech culture of English language. Teaching the etiquette of speech activity from a linguacultural position promotes awareness of common cultural norms, values shared by peoples, stereotypes of thinking and activity, rituals of speech skills accepted by native English speakers. With this approach,

students put their knowledge of English language into practice, while at the same time studying sociocultural speech behavior, mastering the ability to enter into interpersonal interaction with English speakers.

In modern information and communication conditions, the leading role is given to interactivity among students studying English, for the formation of a new type of teacher - a sociocultural personality.

In the field of linguistic training, the main provisions for its improvement are highlighted, oriented "for the interaction of different cultures, their dialogue and mutual enrichment". The above confirms the need to create a social context when mastering English language. Therefore, the assimilation of cultural dialogue is acquiring significance in all areas of intercultural communication at this time. "Among the many aspects of learning English, it is necessary to highlight the problem of improving speech skills in the context of socio-cultural competence for mastering communicative and behavioral culture, which has a deep character and is reflected in all components of foreign language communicative competence: linguistic, sociolinguistic, socio-cultural, discursive, strategic". In the context of the above, there was a need to "modernize English language proficiency based on leading pedagogical technologies. Effective teaching of English can be implemented in the presence of developed communicative competence. A special role in professional activity belongs to socio-cultural and general cultural competence, since they serve active communication with other members of society. Based on the above, many experts suggest paying special attention to the development of speech skills based on a dialogue of socio-cultures, which involves the development of a set of knowledge of the history and modern realities of an English-speaking society, with knowledge of the cultural features, customs and rituals that exist in an English-speaking society.

The work of D.T. Kubeyzinov "Component Analysis of Sentences with Personal Pronouns" is devoted to the study of the component composition of sentences with personal pronouns, the identification and definition of the syntactic relationship between the elements of sentences, differential syntactic features, morphological properties of elementary syntactic units and the suggestible position of personal pronouns in the structure of sentences, as well as the study of the relationship and interdependence of the morphological and syntactic levels of language.

G.N. Tukhlieva believes that colloquial speech is characterized by larger rhythmic divisions, but the slower and more is distinct the speech, the smaller is the rhythmic division. However, of course, there is some limit to such division. A sentence can also be divided into several syntagmas, for example: A 'very 'absent-'minded —>> 'bishop/ was 'once 'travelling by 'train in his 'diocese//. Here "once" and "by train", directly explaining the predicate, are grouped with it in one syntagma, since they are expressed by one word, but if instead of "once" we had, say, 'one 'fine 'summer 'day, then these adverbial words would require a separate syntagma.

The analysis of the works allowed us to come to the conclusion that a major role in improving speech skills belongs to communicative competence, which includes such types of competence as linguistic, speech, sociolinguistic, civilizational, subject, strategic, discursive and communicative, etc.

According to foreign methodologists, the formation of communicative competence is considered the goal of teaching a foreign language. In modern science, for example, I.A. Zimnyaya considers communicative competence also to be the goal of learning, although very distant and not achievable during the training period. At the same time, she interprets communicative

competence both as a result and as a goal of learning. Communicative competence, according to I.A. Zimnyaya, is “the formed ability of a person to act as a subject of communicative activity of communication”. Despite the fact that by now there is no final definition of communicative competence, it can be concluded that communicative competence is understood as possession of complex communicative skills and abilities, formation of adequate skills in new social structures, knowledge of cultural norms and restrictions in communication, knowledge of customs, traditions, etiquette in the sphere of communication, observance of decency, good manners, orientation in communicative means inherent in the national, class mentality and expressed within the framework of a given profession.

Communicative competence is a general communicative property of the individual, including communicative abilities, knowledge and skills, sensory and social experience in the sphere of professional communication. For example, M. Canale and M. Swain identified four main components of communicative competence, which, in interaction with the system of knowledge and skills, form communication.

By grammatical competence they mean vocabulary, phonetics, spelling, semantics and syntax; by sociocultural competence – the correspondence of statements in form and meaning in a specific situation to the contextual background; by discursive competence – the ability to construct holistic, coherent and logical statements in oral and written speech; by strategic competence – compensation by special means for insufficient knowledge of the language, speech and social experience of professional communication in a foreign language environment. (Fig. 1)

Fig.1. The structure of communicative competence according to M.Canale and M.Swain

Foreign language communicative competence (FLCC) has a rather long history of study. At the present stage, there is still no single definition of the term, as well as no consensus on the definition of the component composition of FLCC. Terminological differences are found in the nature of knowledge, skills and abilities that the speaker (listener) operates in the process of generating or reproducing foreign language speech products, as well as in those abilities and qualities that can be developed in the process of mastering a certain set of foreign language knowledge and skills.

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